

AN ANALYSIS OF EIGHTH-GRADE CHEMISTRY TEXTBOOK QUESTIONS IN THE KOSOVAR EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT AND ITS ALIGNMENT WITH THE REVISED BLOOM'S TAXONOMY AND PISA SCIENCE LITERACY

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Abstract

Chemistry textbooks play a crucial role in education, serving as a vital source of knowledge and skills for students in the field of science while also serving as a valuable tool for teachers in various aspects of their instructional practices. These textbooks assist teachers in effectively preparing lessons, designing assignments and assessments, and ensuring that they align with the prescribed curriculum, educational standards, and the overall promotion of student learning (Gilbert et al., 2007; Chen & Eilks, 2019). Incorporating textbook questions and challenges will influence teaching and assessment strategies utilized in scientific educational settings. Moreover, empirical studies have demonstrated that chemistry textbooks are considered valuable educational tools by students (Chen & Eilks, 2019) and an added value to provide an opportunity for them to apply the concepts and principles they have learned in the practical setting (Thomson et al., 2023). Based on international assessments such as PISA, where Kosovar students' scores are substantially lower than the OECD average and the lowest within the region, the fundamental relevance of the science curriculum within scientific education must be addressed (OECD, 2016; OECD, 2019). This study aimed to examine and assess the 8th grade chemistry book end-of-chapter questions used in Kosovo's lower secondary education setting. Moreover, it aimed to provide comprehension of the extent to which these end-of-chapter questions are distributed to the six levels of Bloom's revised taxonomy and PISA requirements for science literacy.

8th-grade Chemistry books and workbooks from lower middle schools in Kosovo, approved by the Ministry of Science and Education, were reviewed with a primary focus on the end-of-chapter questions related to the books' content. Questions have been classified according to revised Bloom's taxonomy and PISA's scientific knowledge competencies, content and context category, and science literacy proficiency scale level. Additionally, the categorization of questions was reviewed based on the type of questions (open-ended, multiple choice, sample solution, matching and filling blanks, and problem-based). The study was guided by the following research questions: 1. What types of end-of-chapter questions are addressed in the commonly used 8th-grade chemistry textbooks? 2. To what extent are end-of-chapter questions from the chemistry textbooks aligned with the PISA requirements? The analyzed research materials consisted of 249 questions from the main book and 579 questions from the workbook from "Dukagjini" publisher and an additional 126 questions from the main book and 348 questions from the workbook within the "Libri shkollor" publisher. The books are perceived as primary resources used by the Kosovar teachers of lower middle schools in Kosovo's education system.

Preliminary findings indicate that within the commonly used general chemistry textbooks, majority of the end-of-chapter questions and problems fall into the category of open questions, with minimal options for the responses (mainly leading to closed answers: yes or no) and hardly providing opportunities to generate critical thinking. Concerning the revised Bloom's taxonomy, most of the end-of-chapter questions require one to remember and understand the content, with very few questions requiring to apply, analyze, and evaluate.

None of them refer to the creation level. In addition, the majority of end-of-chapter questions within the types of scientific knowledge fall into the content knowledge category; questions and requirements are mainly based in the global context, mostly requiring to explain (recognize) within the cognitive category and concerning the PISA scientific literacy proficiency level mainly falling into the 1b and 1a level. The results of this study are expected to reflect not only on a descriptive and comparative overview of the context of the problem but also to provide adequate recommendations that inform policymakers working groups for drafting texts and teaching practices to improve the quality of education, consequently, the results of science literacy. In addition, since the data for the international assessment of PISA include Kosovo as part of the global results, findings from this study would reflect on the possibilities of enhancing the educational system in Kosovo and enabling the internalization of practices and experiences.

Keywords: science literacy, text-book analysis, end-of-chapter questions